

Research Article

NACPMo: Condominium Pricing Model Based on Natural Amenities in Penang

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Abstract: *The Natural Amenities-based Condominium Pricing Model (NACPMo) is a condominium pricing model developed using the Hedonic pricing principle formulated using Ordinary Least Square (OLS). The hedonic pricing principle is a revealed preference model used worldwide in estimating characteristics in the willingness to pay (WTP) for various types of monetary transactions. This principle is adopted to determine the relationship between the condominium price and the natural environment amenities significantly impacting property values in modern landscapes. High-rise structures are the most desirable real estate as cities grow and natural spaces become increasingly expensive. This model can be used to estimate the price of condominiums in the Georgetown, Penang area and contributes valuable insights into the effects of natural amenities on condominium prices in urban areas. The potential buyers can use this model to estimate the costs associated with their desired condominium.*

Keywords: Pricing model; Natural amenities; Ordinary Least Square.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Natural environments, like forests and coastal areas, have long been recognized for their ecological and aesthetic value. In urban settings, these natural environment spaces contribute to the quality of life and can significantly impact property values. The allure of living close to green spaces, coastal areas, rivers, or other natural features can dramatically affect the perceived value of a condominium. The findings of Lee et al. (2023) highlight the positive impact of surrounding green space and visual greenery on apartment prices, suggesting that these features contribute to driving up the value of apartments. Furthermore, Ling Y. (2022) indicates that households can benefit significantly from residing near natural coastlines. The coastal regions provide room for leisure, relaxation, and observation, delivering attractive features for surrounding landscapes. Many potential buyers are drawn to the idea of a serene and picturesque environment where they can enjoy the beauty of nature right at their doorstep.

The condominium developments have undergone substantial changes because of this demand. Based on Hoong (2023), Penang has a sharp increase of about 59% in volume and 68% in value of condominium prices between 2021 and 2022. Living adjacent to a natural forest can affect condominium prices in several ways. Condominiums with stunning views of the forest or close to nature may be more desirable and command higher rates due to their scenic value and the desire for peace. The forest

landscape is one of the most critical factors determining the attractiveness of a building plot (Janeczko et al., 2022). This relationship balances forest proximity's potential benefits and perceived drawbacks in real estate valuation. The proportion of green space in the building's total area and the amount of greenery visible from the main entrance of the building are two characteristics of green spaces in apartment buildings that appear to drive up the cost of units (Lee et al., 2023). Mohd Faris Dziauddin (2013) and Ewane et al. (2023) found that some buyers are willing to spend more on houses with a high value on pleasant landscapes with adjacent forests by using regression models where real estate players begin recognising the amenity benefits. Gillespie et al. (2019) find that the coastal amenities lead to higher sale prices and rental values in the housing industry. Sea views, in terms of depth and breadth, also contribute to the value of condominium properties. Sale price premiums for coastal amenities are typically larger than their rental equivalents, indicating a more substantial effect on the condominium market regarding sale prices. Falling prices in the housing market can amplify the impact of coastal amenities on the condominium market, suggesting that these amenities become more valuable in tighter markets.

Thus, this study aims to establish a condominium pricing model, named NACPMo (Natural Amenities-based for Condominium Pricing Model), which also address the natural amenities in Penang's urban area using an Ordinary Least Square (OLS) of hedonic pricing principle to indicate the proportion of variance in the condominium pricing explained by the chosen natural amenities' variables. In conclusion, the NACPMo may help potential buyers to estimate the price of condominiums in Georgetown, Penang market and ease them in their buying decision-making.

2. METHOD & MATERIAL

Ordinary least squares (OLS) regression determines the relationship between variables of natural amenities and condominium prices. OLS is a regression model that can estimate the coefficient of the variables. The variables are grouped into three types of main preferences: structural, locational, and natural amenities preference variables. Structural preference variables include the size of the built-up area, the number of bedrooms, the age of the condominium building, and many more. Meanwhile, locational variables include the neighborhood characteristics of the condominiums, such as the proximity to important places such as workplaces, main roads, or transportation networks. Incorporating structural and locational preferences used as the control variables in the tested model enhances the model variation explanation by providing a better coefficient of determination (Abdul Wahab et al., 2023). The study's focus variables that will be tested are natural forests and coastlines as natural amenities that influence condominium prices. The model will lead to the relationship's significant influences, magnitude, and direction. The example of the linear model of the functional form of hedonic pricing OLS regression model is shown in eq. (1).

$$PRICE = \beta_0 + \beta_1 SIZE + \beta_2 BEDROOMS + \beta_3 BATHROOMS + \beta_4 MAIN ROAD + \beta_5 TENURE + \beta_6 POOL + \beta_7 PARK + \beta_8 NATURAL AMENITIES + \epsilon \dots\dots\dots (1)$$

Where the dependent variable (PRICE) is formulated by the series of independent variables (depending on the studies); for example, SIZE (house built-up size), BEDROOMS (number of bedrooms), BATHROOMS (number of bathrooms), MAIN ROADS (Proximity to the main roads), TENURE, POOL (1 if yes, = 0 otherwise), PARK (1 if yes, = 0 otherwise), STRUCTURE (1 if yes, = 0 otherwise), ϵ : Error term; β_i : Coefficients; β_0 : Constant.

The selected area for this study is Georgetown, which is situated in Timur Laut District, Penang. It involved 531 samples of transacted condominium units from 2020-2023. The area

is surrounded by natural forest and sea. The transaction data are gathered from Jabatan Penilaian dan Perkhidmatan Harta (JPPH). Figure 1 shows the case study area.

Figure 1. Study area

- (a) Structural Attributes (Built-up area, number of bedrooms, number of bathrooms, building age, total number levels, the existence of facilities (swimming pool, gym, playground, lift, guarded compound), and type of tenure. This data was retrieved from JPPH and supported with Google Earth, site inspection, and property website.
- (b) Locational Attributes (number of public transportation stations, police stations, educational facilities, and hospitals within 1km of the buffer). Data are extracted based on i-Plan’s land use information and Google Earth. The proximity information is analysed using ArcGIS Pro within the required radius.
- (c) Natural amenities attributes (Euclidean distance of natural forest and shoreline to the condominium and view). Data was acquired from satellite imagery and analysed using ArcGIS Pro. The view of the attribute is set by a dichotomous value (1 or 0), where it is assumed to be seen if the distance of forest and shoreline are located within 1km from the condominium unit.

Figure 2. Georgetown area within natural forest and shoreline information

3. FINDINGS

The result of OLS regression, R^2 of 0.736840, provides a percentage of variation in price of 73.7% by the independent variables.

Attribute	Coefficient
Constant	3101
<i>Structural attributes</i>	
Built-up area (in square feet)	684***
Number of bedrooms	1511***
Number of bathrooms	1041***
Building Age	-743***
Total number of levels	3376
Existence of facilities:	
-Swimming pool (1 or 0)	3162
-Gym (1 or 0)	1124
-Playground (1 or 0)	1061
-Lift (1 or 0)	2322
-Guarded compound (1 or 0)	35352
Tenure (1=freehold, 2=leasehold)	-5777**
<i>Locational attributes</i>	
Number of public transportation stations within 1km buffer	1051
Number of police stations within 1km buffer	-1348***
Number of education facilities within 1km buffer	4857*
Number of hospitals within 1km buffer	-2479
<i>Natural amenities attributes</i>	
Proximity to natural forest (km)	184.491***
Proximity to shoreline (km)	265.212
View_natural forest (1 or 0)	512.435***
View_shoreline (1 or 0)	-157.915
R²	0.736840

***p value significant at 0.001

**p value significant at 0.05

*p value significant at 0.01

The result shows that structural variables such as area, number of bedrooms, number of bathrooms, building age, and tenure significantly influence the price of a condominium at 0.001. According to the locational attributes, proximity to the police station has a significant negative influence on the price at the 0.001 level, whereas educational facilities have a positive impact on the price at the 0.01 significant level. This suggests that a house near the police station may cause a price decrease, which seems unlikely to be the best choice. However, people tend to live near educational facilities, like schools or higher education facilities. Proximity to educational facilities may increase condominium prices as it is easier for them to commute.

According to the result of natural amenities, Table 1 shows that the impact of the natural forest positively affects the condominium price, with a p-value of 0.001 both in terms of proximity and view. However, the shoreline does not significantly impact the condominium price. This could be due to the desire for a calming sea view, which is more enjoyable in the Batu Feringhi area than in Georgetown, where much of the shoreline is protected by coastal armour to prevent erosion.

Hence, the NACPMo is formulated as follow:

Price = 3101 + 684 (Built-up area) + 1511 (number of bedroom) + 1041 (number of bathrooms) – 743 (Building age) – 5777 (type of tenure) – 1348 (number of nearby police stations) + 4857 (number of nearby education facilities + 184.491 (proximity of natural forest) + 512.435 (view of natural forest) + ε

4. DISCUSSION

Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) regression is a fundamental statistical technique used to analyze linear relationships between variables. One of its key assumptions is that the observations in the dataset are independent of one another. In the context of the NACPMo, it has been observed that natural amenities—such as natural forests—play a significant role in influencing condominium prices in Georgetown, Penang. This relationship highlights the economic value that natural surroundings can have on real estate. However, there is room for improvement in the analysis. For example, implementing spatial hedonic pricing, which considers the geographical characteristics of properties and their surroundings, could lead to more reliable and nuanced data on pricing trends.

5. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the OLS regression analysis (NACPMo) highlights that condominium prices in Georgetown, Penang, are significantly influenced by structural features (like built-up area, number of bedrooms, and tenure), proximity to educational facilities, and natural amenities such as proximity to and views of natural forests. The findings underscore the value residents place on educational convenience and natural surroundings, while factors like police station proximity show an unexpected negative impact. To enhance accuracy, future studies could incorporate spatial hedonic pricing models, offering a more precise understanding of how geographic factors shape real estate prices in the area.

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